

ECONOMIC PARTICIPATION OF CITIZENS AND LOCAL STAKEHOLDERS IN WIND ENERGY

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ABOUT

Wind lab 2 focuses on fostering community and citizen-led economic participation in wind energy projects in Central and Northern Portugal, particularly repowering investments, either through co financing mechanisms (such as crowdlending) or co ownership structures (such as energy cooperatives).

KEY TOPICS

- Absence of collective ownership or community financed wind energy projects in Portugal
- Growing public resistance to wind energy developments
- Low or residual distributive justice for local stakeholders from wind energy projects
- Low procedural justice for local stakeholders regarding wind energy plans and projects

GUIDELINES

Municipalities and regional energy agencies have a pivotal role in promoting a just energy transition and should use the legal, fiscal and economic tools at their disposal in a proactive way to rebalance power dynamics between promoters and citizens at the local level;

Policy instruments, particularly regulatory changes that empower local ownership and make local economic participation of citizens mandatory, are unavoidable strategies to force market agents to embrace energy justice principles, particularly in wind energy;

The meaningful economic participation of citizens in wind energy projects requires early investments in energy literacy, financial literacy and energy democracy, particularly in socio-cultural realities where these are lower;

Allowing citizens to invest, through crowdlending, or being a member of a wind energy project is not per se a guarantee of inclusivity and distributive justice as even the access for these opportunities might be biased for those already with financial or social status. **Further conditions need to be made to guarantee that the “energy poor” and those more susceptible to the energy burden can participate and directly benefit.**